

Deliverable 5.2.2.1

INTEGRATED NFDI4ENERGY SIMULATION SCENARIO ONTOLOGY
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Integrated NFDI4Energy simulation scenario ontology

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Table of Contents

General Information	3
Summary	3
Deliverable within NFDI4Energy	3
Deliverable	4
Introduction	4
Ontology Development Process	4
Modeled Concepts	6
Simulation Scenario	6
Simulation Component	8
Simulation Connection	9
Other concepts	10
Future Work	11
Conclusion	11
Acknowledgements.....	12
List of Acronyms	12

General Information

Summary

The primary objective of Task 5.2.2 in NFDI4Energy is to develop a scenario ontology for co-simulation and to facilitate the creation of simulation scenarios. As a first step, we examined available ontologies and evaluated their relevance for this use case, as described in a previous deliverable [1]. Based on this preliminary work, we decided to use the Open Energy Ontology (OEO) as a basis for our development and to add new concepts for the definition of simulation scenarios [2].

The most essential concepts for the description of co-simulation, are the scenarios, components, and connections. In this context, scenario is a general term for the description of a simulation, consisting of different simulation components and the connections between them, which describe the data flows in a simulation. We modeled these concepts in the OEO to provide a basis for the description and annotation of co-simulation scenarios. Additional concepts may be added in the future to provide more details.

Clear description and systematic annotation of simulation scenarios are essential because they standardize terminology and configuration, which lead to improved interoperability across diverse co-simulation frameworks and reduces the manual effort required to align heterogeneous models and tools. This standardization also supports automated discovery of compatible components, automated compatibility checks, and scalable scenario deployment (e.g., within Simulation-as-a-Service (SimaaS) infrastructures). Moreover, well-annotated scenarios enhance reproducibility and FAIRness of simulation experiments by making scenario definitions easier to share, compare, and reuse across research projects and platforms.

Deliverable within NFDI4Energy

Task Area 5 addresses simulation in interdisciplinary energy research with Measure 5.2 specifically focused on developing ontological support for co-simulation in the energy domain. Previously, we published our evaluation of existing ontologies as a deliverable of Task 5.2.1 [1]. In Task 4.1.4, the “Technische Informationsbibliothek” – German National Library of Science and Technology (TIB) - provides a Terminology Service (TS), which offers collections of ontologies and a common interface to retrieve terminological information. We added the most relevant and openly available ontologies from Task 5.2.1 to the NFDI4Energy collection in the TS [3].

The scenario ontology described in this deliverable of Task 5.2.2 also serves as a foundation for subsequent tasks within Measure 5.2. Based on the ontology and a registry of simulation software from Measure 5.1, the next task in Measure 5.2 is the development of processes to support the users in the development of simulation scenarios. Additionally, the ontology will be used for the integration of the three co-simulation frameworks DaceDSX [4], VILLASframework [5], and mosaik [6] into the planned Simulation-as-a-Service hub [7] in Measures 5.3 and 5.4.

This work is closely aligned with Measure 4.1 (“Energy system research ontology”), which establishes a working group (Task 4.1.1) to coordinate efforts on metadata and ontologies across the consortium. In this “Working Group Metadata and Ontologies” the different ontology development tasks of NFDI4Energy are discussed to facilitate mutual learning and to identify potential collaborative tasks relevant to multiple teams working on different tasks. For example, joined work is planned on a mapping between the OEO and the Common Information Model (CIM) [8].

Deliverable

Introduction

Co-simulation, executed across multiple solvers, enables the integration of heterogeneous models, allowing researchers to couple different domains and analyze complex multi-domain interactions within energy systems. To support seamless tool interoperability and reproducible scenario definitions, NFDI4-Energy is developing a comprehensive ontology that standardizes terminology and serves as a configuration reference for simulation frameworks. It is being developed as part of a broader NFDI4Energy effort to support FAIR data principles and will be integrated with existing resources, the Open Energy Platform (OEP) and the OEO, as well as planned NFDI4Energy services such as the SimaaS hub and a registry of simulation models. These integrations aim to streamline simulation configuration, enhance scalability, support automated discovery and compatibility checks, and reduce manual effort in aligning models with scenario requirements, ultimately advancing the efficiency and reproducibility of energy system research.

An overview of existing ontologies in the context of energy system research was already provided in [9], and in [1] simulation ontologies were evaluated based on their representation of simulation scenarios. The energy-focused ontologies can be relevant for the semantic description of simulation components, but the ontologies in the overviews lack representation of simulation scenarios as shown in [1], [9]. Therefore, only a few aspects contained in the collected ontologies are relevant for a scenario ontology and might be reused.

Many different co-simulation frameworks exist in the energy research domain. For our work the three frameworks mosaik, DaceDSX, and VILLASframework will be exemplarily integrated as they represent a broad range of different types of co-simulation. Mosaik represents an established software co-simulation framework with focus on user-friendly flexible scenario creation [6], [10]. DaceDSX uses a publish-subscribe-middleware approach and was originally developed for the traffic domain, but is adapted to energy system simulation [4]. VILLASframework enables distributed real-time co-simulation with integration of hardware devices [5].

The concept of scenario exhibits significant variation across simulation frameworks, accompanied by inconsistent terminology that impedes interoperability. To address this challenge, a general simulation scenario ontology is proposed, comprising core concepts existing in all frameworks while permitting extension through framework-specific modules. This structure enables alignment of diverse frameworks with a common foundational architecture, concurrently allowing detailed modeling within dedicated modules. Although full interoperability remains unattainable due to inherent framework heterogeneity, the ontology facilitates the development of a unified toolkit for discovering simulation components and supporting scenario construction and comparative analysis. Consequently, this approach specifically enhances structural interoperability for component identification and scenario design, bridging critical terminology gaps without requiring full execution-level compatibility.

In the following, we will give an overview of the development of the co-simulation scenario ontology tailored for co-simulation of energy systems. We describe the general Ontology Development Process and the concrete Modeled Concepts. We present our plans for Future Work and our Conclusion.

Ontology Development Process

We followed the LOT methodology [11] for ontology development. It distinguishes the four main steps *requirements specification*, *implementation*, *publication*, and *maintenance* of ontologies (see Figure 1). The *requirements specification* for the co-simulation scenario ontology was already described in [12] and led to the decision to develop no new ontology, but to integrate our concepts in the OEO [13]. We considered an alternative design in which a separate ontology, aligned with the OEO, would have been introduced. However, this approach was rejected because most of the concepts we intend to model are close to concepts, that already existed within the *oao-model* module of the OEO [2]. The OEO itself is organized in modules: a central file orchestrates imports from a suite of specialized sub-modules and from external ontologies, thereby ensuring coherence while preserving extensibility. Consequently,

Figure 1: Overview of the Linked Open Terms (LOT) approach with focus on the implementation.

we extended the existing *oeo-model* module with our new concepts. This module “covers entities for models, assumptions, parameters, data, software and all the processes that transform these, including model execution and data transformation” [14], making it a good place to incorporate our additions. Due to the integration in the OEO, the steps *publication* and *maintenance* of the LOT are mostly covered by existing infrastructure of the OEO. For the *implementation* step we still tried to follow the LOT approach, but adapted it in some aspects because we did not start from scratch as it is described in LOT. The implementation is subdivided into the following four sub-steps in the LOT approach:

Ontology conceptualization: The goal is to create a model representing the domain. This can be done in a formal system or in diagrams. For diagrams the *Chowlk* notation, *UML_Ont* profile, or entity relationship diagrams can be used.

Ontology reuse: To improve interoperability, the reuse of existing ontologies is helpful in the form of importing (hard reuse) or referencing the Uniform Resource Identifiers (URIs) of ontology elements (soft reuse). Even though, the evaluation is located in the implementation step, the LOT proposes to take it into account also in other steps, like the requirements specification.

Ontology encoding: In this step, the previously created model is transformed into an ontology implementation language, like Web Ontology Language (OWL).

Ontology evaluation: After the encoding of the ontology, evaluation aims to check the technical quality of the ontology by comparing it with the defined requirements and the domain model.

Our realization of the implementation is depicted in Figure 2. We started already in the requirements specification to collect crucial terms and concepts for the description of co-simulation scenarios based on the three reference frameworks and external existing ontologies [1], [12]. Everything was collected in a Conceptboard¹. Although the LOT methodology proposes the use of strict tooling and clear notation for ontology concepts for this step, we decided to use this more flexible tool to facilitate collaboration and to promote participation for people without large ontology modeling experience. After collecting terms,

¹Conceptboard is an online visual collaboration platform that provides a shared whiteboard where teams can brainstorm, sketch, annotate, and organize ideas collaboratively in real time (<https://www.conceptboard.com>).

Figure 2: Overview of the ontology implementation process and alignment with the LOT methodology (blue arrows) [15].

we clustered them into different concepts to have better structure for our discussion and the integration in the OEO and focus on one concept at a time, even though there are sometimes connections to other concepts. For each concept we started to get them in a more ontology-compliant form. One part of this was to check the OEO for already existing concepts for potential reuse. So, we chose a definition and a potential parent class for each term and also added relations between the different terms, which can represent *is_a* relationships as well as other object properties.

Because we decided to integrate our concepts into the OEO [1], [16], which is based on the Basic Formal Ontology (BFO) [17], we had to map our concepts into the existing class hierarchy. The BFO distinguishes between entities that persist through time (*continuants*) and those that unfold temporally (*occurents*). Occurents comprise, for example, *processes* that represent dynamic activities. Continuants are further divided into *independent continuants*—including *material entities* such as physical objects and *immaterial entities* like spatial regions—and two types of dependent continuants. First, *generically dependent continuant (GDC)*, which cannot exist in isolation but must be inherently attached to some independent bearer. A prominent subclass of these are *information content entities (ICE)*, which is a GDC “about some thing”. Second, the *specifically dependent continuant (SDC)*, which also cannot exist in isolation, but depends on one specific bearer and can not be moved to another bearer.

We documented concepts after our internal discussion in GitHub issues and discussed them with the OEO developer team to get feedback for further refinement. Approved concepts were then encoded in OWL and added to the OEO. For the evaluation, we are using the ontology to annotate simulation scenarios of our co-simulation frameworks.

Modeled Concepts

Each concept we modeled is based on one cluster of terms we identified at the beginning of the development process. We describe them in the following, starting with the most important concepts: Simulation Scenario, Simulation Component, and Simulation Connection, but also mentioning Other concepts which are under discussion and will be modeled and implemented in the future.

As the modeling mainly was done in a Conceptboard, we add for each concept a screenshot of the corresponding part (e.g., see Figure 3). The green boxes represent the label of a class and lighter green boxes the definition, blue boxes represent classes from OEO which are reused and existed already before, the blue ellipsis stand for the parent class. Arrows between the boxes represent object properties.

Simulation Scenario

Obviously, the most central concept of a simulation scenario ontology is the *simulation scenario*. The OEO contained already the term *scenario*, and one option would have been to define simulation scenario as subclass of scenario, but one important rule of the OEO development process is, that classes should arise from concepts rather than from words. Looking at the definition, we found that the focus

Figure 3: Simulation scenario concept modeled in Conceptboard [15].

of the scenario term is more on future scenarios, which were more in focus of the OEO than simulation scenarios until now: “A scenario is an information content entity that contains statements about a possible future development based on a coherent and internally consistent set of assumptions and their motivation” [14]. A simulation scenario usually also contains a set of assumptions about future development, but the focus is more on the description of a concrete simulation run and all the necessary parts to be able to execute it. Thus, we identified *plan specification* as parent class. To avoid confusion between the existing scenario term in the OEO and the new class, we use *simulation plan specification* as main label and scenario scenario as alternative label (see Figures 3 and 4). In the following, we will still use the term simulation scenario, as this is the common term in the domain.

While the simulation scenario also contains the motivation and planned analysis, which will be done based on the simulation results, we added a second class representing the technical part of a simulation scenario. We defined the term *simulation configuration*, which is *part of* the simulation scenario and contains all technical description to run a simulation: *simulation components, connections, and data*.

The term plan specification was already imported in the OEO and originally comes from the Information Artifact Ontology (IAO). It is defined as “A directive information entity with action specifications and objective specifications as parts, and that may be concretized as a realizable entity that, if realized, is realized in a process in which the bearer tries to achieve the objectives by taking the actions specified” [18]. The *action specification describes an action the bearer will take*. For a simulation configuration this could be, for example, the steps of initializing and starting the simulation components and starting the simulation process. As the modeling of those steps is not in our focus for now, we did not model action specifications.

The *objective specifications describe intended process endpoints*, which will be achieved after the process. We defined two new objective specifications: one is the quite generic *output creation objective*, which might be reused by a broad range of classes and the other is the *output data creation objective* focusing on creation of data as it is always the case for a simulation configuration. In the future, we might add more concrete subclasses for specific types of output needed for the analysis (e.g., grid sta-

description is to represent also Hardware-in-the-Loop (HiL) approaches, which have hardware devices integrated in a simulation. Thus, simulation components can be differentiated between the *hardware simulation component* directly representing actual hardware, or the simulation model that simulates the behaviour based on algorithms or mathematical expressions. The OEO contains already the term *simulation model* with the definition: “A simulation model is a model that simulates the behaviour of a system without a target function.” It is subclass of *numerical computer model*, which is subclass of *mathematical model*. At the start of the discussion, we were critical that this definition fits to our understanding of a simulation model, because they are usually some kind of software and do not have to contain explicit formulas. But we decided to use the existing class, because every programmed computer model represents a mathematical model. In the future this can also be aligned with the Modelling UNcertainties Ontology (MUNO), which might be integrated in the OEO [20].

Before thinking about the integration into the OEO, we planned to make simulation component the parent class of simulation model and the hardware interface. Due to the *principle of single inheritance*, which is part of the BFO best practices [17], this was not possible, because the simulation model would have multiple parent classes. Thus, we added a *simulation component role*, and the *simulation component*, which is a “software that bears the simulation component role and is eligible to be referenced in a simulation configuration.” (see also Figure 5).

To model the simulation component representing the interface which is used to integrate hardware devices into simulation we created the simulation hardware component. The definition of the term *hardware* existed in the OEO, but was only mentioning electronic systems. Thus, we changed its label to *electronic hardware* to clarify it. In most cases for a HiL simulation, electronic hardware will be the correct class, but to not exclude, for example, thermal systems, we decided to use a broader term. Currently the best fitting class is the parent class of electronic hardware—the *artificial object*. The Common Core Ontology (CCO) [21] contains the term *material artifact*, which is even better, because it is not referencing the purpose but the function of a thing. Thus, we propose to import it in the OEO.

Another term from the CCO, which is already imported in the OEO, is *represents*. We use it to model the relationship between the simulation hardware component and the artificial object or material artifact. In HiL simulation, the hardware device, which is tested, is usually called *device under test*. To represent this device in the OEO we add the *device under test role*.

The concept is currently under final discussion with the OEO developer team and there might be still changes. It is planned to be part of the next release of version 2.12.0 in summer of 2026.

Simulation Connection

Figure 6: Simulation connection concept modeled in Conceptboard.

The previously described simulation components must be connected to have data flows between them and execute a simulation scenario. The connection between the simulation components are modeled quite differently in the frameworks. In DaceDSX the connections are not defined in the scenario configuration, because the data flows are based on Kafka topics which are defined inside of the simulation components. We identified the general concepts of the three frameworks, and modeled the simulation connections concept as visualized in Figure 6.

Simulation components can have multiple *simulation connection ports*, which are the available in- and

outputs of a simulation component. The in- and outputs are modeled as subclasses of the simulation connection port.

The connection between simulation components and their ports is modeled as a *quality*: (*"a quality is a specifically dependent continuant that, in contrast to roles and dispositions, does not require any further process in order to be realized"*). In contrast to the GDC, the SDC is dependent on one specific continuant, which fits to simulation connections being dependent on the simulation component instance. The simulation connection ports can be realized in a *simulation connection*, which is a *relational quality* and is realized in a concrete data flow in the simulation.

For the more detailed description of the simulation connection port, we defined the *message schema* and *message attribute*, which are both a *data format specification*. A simulation connection port has one message schema, which can have n message attributes.

Connected to the simulation connection, the *message modification* stands for specific modifications that are made in the data flow between simulation components. The final integration into the OEO is still open and will be discussed.

There are still open discussions about the message modification and the other parts of the concept have to be concluding discussed. Thus, the release of this concept is planned to be part of the next release of version 2.12.0 in summer of 2026.

Other concepts

Besides the described terms for definition of scenarios, we have some terms on a list, which have not yet been modeled in detail, but the discussion has just started and they will be added later.

General simulation terms During our discussion of the presented concepts, we already discussed general simulation terms and how to differentiate between them. These are terms like *co-simulation*, *distributed simulation*, *parallel simulation*, *hardware-in-the-loop*, *simulation software*, *simulation framework*, *simulation tool*. We agreed already on definitions for the most relevant terms of the list, but did not yet model them in detail in the OEO. It might be helpful for discussions in the future, to add the definitions also to the ontology.

Parameter Usually, simulation components can be used for different use cases within simulation frameworks and allow to be configured accordingly with parameters. The parameters can be on different levels:

System-level: A parameter configures the processing units on which the simulation is running and is the same for multiple simulation configurations running on the same system. This can be, for example, the address of a service like Kafka for DaceDSX.

Simulation configuration-level: A Parameter is part of the the simulation configuration, like for example, the time which is simulated (e.g., a week, a year). The parameter is associated with the simulation configuration.

Component-level: A parameter adjusts one component for the scenario. For example, the size of a PV system is defined in a PV simulator, or a grid is chosen in a grid simulator. The parameter is associated with the simulation component and the simulation configuration the simulation component is part of.

The OEO contains already the *program parameter* with the definition *"A program parameter is a variable in a software."*. One option to model the parameters would be to create subclasses for the three different levels. Alternatively, the different levels could be modeled by adding relationships of the program parameter to the simulation configuration and simulation component.

Future Work

We added already the first concepts to the OEO, but presented also concepts which are still under discussion and must be added in the future. In general, the ontology development will be an ongoing process, that will support upcoming implementation of the SimaaS hub and scenario creation process. Beyond the general technical definition of scenarios, also domain-specific aspects have to be considered. For simulation of energy systems usually a grid topology is needed, which is a crucial part of the scenario definition, because additional simulation models are usually mapped to it. Thus, the specification of a grid topology has to be also part of the scenario ontology and the integration of a suitable standard, like for example the CIM [8], is planned. Additionally, semantic concepts of energy systems modeled already in the OEO might be used in the future to better annotate simulation scenarios or better describe the data flows or support the user in connecting the right simulation components.

Conclusion

We presented a scenario ontology for co-simulation of energy systems that extends the OEO to provide a data model for scenario definition in frameworks such as mosaik, DaceDSX, and VILLASframework. Building on a list of terms already identified during the requirements-specification step, we organized the terms on a Conceptboard and aligned the derived concepts—simulation scenario, simulation configuration, simulation components, connections, and simulation parameter—with the OEO's and BFO's class hierarchy, reusing existing classes where appropriate. The ontology has been encoded in OWL, added to the oeo-model module, and is already used to annotate example simulation scenarios, while further extensions are planned to support the upcoming SimaaS hub and model registry. The development is focusing on the three co-simulation frameworks VILLASframework, DaceDSX, and mosaik, but should also be reusable for other frameworks. Thus, an export of our Conceptboard is available as additional material to our publication [22] and discussions on GitHub [19] are open to feedback on the concepts.

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List of Acronyms

- BFO** Basic Formal Ontology. 6, 9, 11
- CCO** Common Core Ontology. 9
- CIM** Common Information Model. 3, 11
- GDC** generically dependent continuant. 6, 10
- HiL** Hardware-in-the-Loop. 9
- IAO** Information Artifact Ontology. 7
- ICE** information content entity. 6
- LOT** Linked Open Terms. 4–6
- MUNO** Modelling UNCertainties Ontology. 9
- OEO** Open Energy Ontology. 3–11
- OEP** Open Energy Platform. 4
- OWL** Web Ontology Language. 5, 11
- SDC** specifically dependent continuant. 6, 10
- SimaaS** Simulation-as-a-Service. 3, 4, 11
- URI** Uniform Resource Identifier. 5

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